

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

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INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON ECONOMIC GROWTH OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Igamberdiyeva Kunduz Ergashevna

Tashkent State University of Transport Associate Professor department
"Account and Business"

Abstract: Digital transformation contributes to the emergence of new business models and the introduction of new digital solutions, which are a driver for increasing the efficiency of business processes. In addition, the digital transformation of industries and areas of the national economy contributes to an increase in the efficiency of labor productivity, improvement of business processes, an increase in jobs in the field of digital technologies, an improvement in the quality of life based on an increase in the speed of information exchange, the availability and security of information, and the development of innovative technological solutions.

Key words: regulatory framework, digital transformation, main macroeconomic indicators, digital development, digital infrastructure, digital business models, digital platforms, economic growth, quality of life of the population.

Annotatsiya: Raqamli transformatsiya biznes-jarayonlari samaradorligini oshirish uchun harakatlantiruvchi omil bo'lgan yangi biznes modellarining paydo bo'lishiga va yangi raqamli yechimlarning joriy etilishiga yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari, milliy iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari va yo'nalishlarini raqamli transformatsiya qilish mehnat unumdorligi samaradorligini oshirish, biznes jarayonlarini takomillashtirish, raqamli texnologiyalar sohasida ish o'rinlarini ko'paytirish, hayot sifatini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Axborot almashish tezligini oshirish, axborotning mavjudligi va xavfsizligini ta'minlash, innovatsion texnologik yechimlarni ishlab chiqish.

Kalit so'zlar: me'yoriy-huquqiy baza, raqamli transformatsiya, asosiy makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar, raqamli rivojlanish, raqamli infratuzilma, raqamli biznes modellari, raqamli platformalar, iqtisodiy o'sish, aholi turmush sharti.

Аннотация: Цифровая трансформация способствует появлению новых бизнес-моделей и внедрению новых цифровых решений, которые являются драйвером повышения эффективности бизнес-процессов. Кроме того, цифровая трансформация отраслей и сфер национальной экономики способствует повышению эффективности производительности труда, совершенствованию бизнес-процессов, увеличению количества рабочих мест в сфере цифровых технологий, улучшению качества жизни на основе повышение скорости обмена информацией, доступности и безопасности информации, разработка инновационных технологических решений.

Ключевые слова: нормативно-правовая база, цифровая трансформация, основные макроэкономические показатели, цифровое развитие, цифровая инфраструктура, цифровые бизнес-модели, цифровые платформы, экономический рост, качество жизни населения.

In 2017, a new version of the Unified Portal of Interactive Government Services (my.gov.uz) was launched, and the National Project Management Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created. And in 2018, the Digital Trust Fund for Supporting the Development of the Digital Economy was formed with the aim of attracting and consolidating investor funds for the implementation of projects in the field on public-private partnership terms, including those related to the implementation of blockchain technology.

Also, the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the Year of Development of Science, Education and Digital Economy provides for the implementation of large-scale tasks and projects determined by the President in the field of development of the digital economy and e-government.

In order to further develop information technologies, the Presidential Decree "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government" was adopted on April 28, 2020. The document sets out comprehensive measures to fulfill the assigned tasks. A draft Decree of the Head of State "On the strategy for the development of artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2022" has been developed and posted on SOVAZ.

As follows from the Decrees and Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the digital economy, by 2022 in Uzbekistan the share of electronic government services is planned to increase to 60%.

The resolution also provides for the development of “digital entrepreneurship” with an increase in the volume of services in this area by three times by 2023 and bringing their exports to \$100 million.

Widespread introduction of digital technologies is planned at all stages of the education system. By 2022, digital knowledge training centers will open in all regions of the country as part of the “Five Initiatives” project.

The Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications has been designated as the authorized body in the field of development of the digital economy and e-government. The National Agency for Project Management under the President retains the authority to implement crypto-assets and blockchain technology.

Two new institutions will be formed under the ministry:

- “E-Government Project Management Center”;
- “Digital Economy Research Center”.

In the structure of the central apparatus of the ministry, the position of deputy minister has been introduced, responsible for issues of accelerated digitalization of the agricultural sector, the introduction of modern information systems and software products in the agriculture and food security sectors. The Ministry of Infocom is also creating a department for the development of digital technologies in the agricultural sector and a department for the development of geoinformation technologies.

In addition, the state share in the authorized capital of LLC “Unified integrator for the creation and support of state information systems UZINFOCOM” is transferred free of charge to the Ministry of Information Technology.

Modern reality shows that the Republic of Uzbekistan has currently developed a “Road Map”, approved within the framework of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy and measures for its effective implementation,” which provides for the development of the following areas:

- development of the e-government system”;
- development of the digital industry;
- development of digital education;
- development of digital infrastructure.

At the same time, data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics show that in January 2021, the share of telecommunications services (wired, mobile, satellite communication services, Internet) amounted to 74.8%.

In turn, digitalization is a driver for the development of industries and areas of the national economy.

In table 1 presents the main macroeconomic indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan over the past 5 years.

Table 1: Main macroeconomic indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Indicator name	Unit	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Gross domestic product	billion soums	242,495.5	302536.8	406,648.5	511,838.1	580 203.2
Industrial products	billion soums	111,869.4	148,846.0	235 340.7	331,006.6	367,078.9
Consumer goods	billion soums	48,253.8	59,690.4	83,512.6	111,494.3	119 159.8
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	billion soums	119,726.7	154,369.4	195 103.7	224,288.8	260 306.8
Industrial products	billion soums	111,869.4	148,846.0	235 340.7	331,006.6	367,078.9
Consumer goods	billion soums	48,253.8	59,690.4	83,512.6	111,494.3	119 159.8
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	billion soums	119,726.7	154,369.4	195 103.7	224,288.8	260 306.8
Industrial products	billion soums	111,869.4	148,846.0	235 340.7	331,006.6	367,078.9
Consumer goods	billion soums	48,253.8	59,690.4	83,512.6	111,494.3	119 159.8
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	billion soums	119,726.7	154,369.4	195 103.7	224,288.8	260 306.8
Industrial products	billion soums	111,869.4	148,846.0	235 340.7	331,006.6	367,078.9

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics.

The rate of GDP growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan by type of economic activity for 2022 (as a percentage of the previous year) is presented in Fig. 1.

Research by specialists in the field of digital technologies indicates that the main macroeconomic indicator is gross domestic product, which characterizes the final result of the production activities of resident economic units, which is measured by the cost of goods and services produced by these units for final use.

Fig. 1: GDP growth rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan by type of economic activity for 2022 (in% of the previous year)

Source: www.stat.uz – data from the official portal of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics.

Based on the research results, we can conclude that the formation of the digital economy provides the following areas of development in the national economy:

- creation of a new information infrastructure, in particular, the development of high-speed Internet access, wireless communications, 5G networks, etc.;
- development of end-to-end digital technologies, including cloud and additive technologies, Internet of things, robotics, etc.;
- transformation of society and business, which, in turn, includes the digital literacy of every individual citizen and employee, as well as the comprehensive development of the individual;
- convergence of technologies;
- formation and development of new business models;
- development and implementation of new digital platforms;
- increasing digital literacy, etc.;
- development and improvement of information and cyber security systems

As practice shows, in the context of the digital transformation of the global economic system, industries and spheres of the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are increasingly using the potential of digital technological solutions that contribute to achieving competitive advantages in the global economic market. This approach implies not only the modernization of technical equipment, software updates or intellectualization of production, but also fundamental changes in management processes, corporate culture and external commu-

nications. In turn, improving management contributes to the growth of labor productivity of each employee, optimization of information exchange, robotization and intellectualization of labor, which ultimately serves to achieve high results in the economic market.

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